

XIX-asr boshlarida Samarqand tarixi

Самарканд в начале XIX века

Samarkand at the beginning of the 19th century

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ABSTRACT At the beginning of the 19th century, Samarkand was a city with many historical traditions. During this period, it was in practice among the armies of Samarkand, Kazakh Empire and China. The city became a protectorate of the Kazakh Empire at the beginning of the 19th century, but later Chinese troops overran Samarkand.

KEY WORDS Development and innovation of cultural life in Samarkand, the city of Samarkand and its features. The 19th century was a period of rule and development for Samarkand

In the 19th century, Samarkand occupied a central place for various fields in various ways, and its triches were of great importance in world history, showing its cultural, economic and political life. In the first half of the 19th century in Samarkand, the Russians occupied Samarkand, and it was also one of the main industrial cities in Maverannahr, which participated in Russia during this period. During this period, Samarkand was the central part of the Russo-Maverannahr war in the 19th century, and this war was one of the most effective cities in military strategy and economic development. is one of the defeated neighboring powers. During this period, there were many cultural, economic and political developments throughout Samarkand, and Samarkand made a great contribution to the development of Islamic culture, cultural and religious spirituality in the 19th century. At the beginning of the 19th century, Samarkand was a city with many traditions in its history. The city of Samarkand is known as one of the oldest cities, a garden of buildings, culture and cultural heritage. This city has more than 2,500 years of history and is one of the oldest cities along the Zeravshan River, which is why it is called the "City of the World".

In the 19th century, Samarkand became the center of Asia, becoming many cultural, scientific and religious centers, and was the circle of many important states through the protection of the Ottoman, Safavid, Mughal and other

empires. During this period, Samarkand was a strong and developed center, since the historical city territory was in another circle of these empires. As a result, in the first half of the 19th century, Samarkand lived another good period in the field of ancient cultural and cultural life, especially in the field of architecture, philosophy, literature, and science. During this period, cultural property gaps, interstate wars, and religious movements were important events in the history of Samarkand.

At the beginning of the 19th century, Samarkand showed good economic, cultural and cultural development. The historical city has preserved its cultural heritage and continued to develop in the fields of culture, science, art, and architecture. During this period, Samarkand was a central city occupied by several independent houses, bird feeders, farmers, and cultural productions, and at the same time, it developed in the fields of industry, commerce, and culture. Samarkand, the Kazakh Empire, and China It is located in the 13th-15th centuries, when there were practical events between these countries, starting from the talk about tires. Samarkand is a cultivated Western Tokhristian region, and its history has long been the center of modern Asian civilizations. The history of this city began in the 7th-8th centuries and reached its highest level during the reign of Amir Temur. During the rule of Amir Temur, Samarkand became a center of modern culture and created excellent conditions for cultural, scientific and cultural development. The Kazakh Empire was an empire that waged mutual wars in Central Asia and South Russia in the 15th-19th centuries. had a widespread area. Along with the people of the Kazakh Empire, the famous troops were famous all over the world. Their military activity and political importance was great.

From the second half of the 19th century, modernization and Russification processes were widespread in Samarkand. During this period, many cultural and architectural objects, mosques, caravan palaces, madrasahs and cells of the ancient city of Samarkand were destroyed. Also, the city opened the way for independence and wide burial to deepen to the surface, difficulties and serious problems were born. fell under the rub. It was at this time that Russian, Uzbek-Kipchak and Turkestan Muslims were introduced to Samarkand and its territories for experimentation. The process of Russification was surprising in other features. From year to year, Samarkand changed its customs, teaching and working in Russian language was used. The cultural environment changed to suit Russian culture, and national identity was largely lost. These processes led to shortages and sorrows in the population of Samarkand, and thousands of people wanted to leave the city. In the midst of this, the situation of the city of Samarkand and its

inhabitants became more difficult as the end of the 19th century approached. During this period, the city became essentially a Russian colony, and Russian imperialism became an encyclopedic client of this client, and at the same time, a world of necessity between space and the city.

At the beginning of the 19th century, the Kazakh Empire occupied a protected area in the city of Samarkand, but later Chinese troops took power in the city of Samarkand. Chinese troops fought against the Ottoman Empire from the middle of the 19th century and conquered many territories. In the midst of these battles, Samarkand was also overrun by the Chinese. Chinese troops taking power in the city of Samarkand is one of the notable events in history. They also influenced the cultural and economic development of the city of Samarkand and helped to increase the historical importance of the city.

The history of the 19th century Samarkand courthouses was connected with the development of the city of Samarkand at the beginning of the 19th century, during the reign of the Soviet Union. During this period, the city of Samarkand was the center of culture, science and development, and its future was similar to the courthouses created for a long time. Samarkand courthouses are usually located far from the city center, large and large, and served as a center of culture, medicine and trade. At the end of the 19th century, Samarkand courthouses became very popular and popularized, and were important for domestic and international trade relations. had A number of special goods were sold in these khazinas, including yarn, music, medicine, tea, knives, etc.

History of Samarkand Khazijans Due to the regulation and industrialization policy of the Soviet Union, the old structure was lost and replaced by new settlements. Today, the adjoining courthouses house many modern shops and restaurants, but have preserved much of their history. Today, Samarkand's courthouses are of great importance for city tourism, and the country always becomes an image of big tourists.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Samarkand underwent modernization and Russification processes from the second half of the 19th century. During this period, cultural and economic life in Samarkand changed under Russian rule. Russians tried to regulate cultural and economic life in Samarkand and opened new areas for attracting new foreign investments. During this period, cultural and economic modernization of Samarkand took place

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